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FORMULATION AND EVALUATION OF HYDROXYAPATITE MICROSPHERES OF AN ANTIMICROBIAL DRUG FOR THE TREATMENT OF OSTEOMYELITIS

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ABSTRACT

This study was intended to formulate, characterize, evaluate in-vitro formulation release a dissolution studies of hydroxyapatite included microspheres of an antimicrobial drug for t disease osteomyelitis. Levofloxacin stacked hydroxyapatite microspheres were set up by inotro gelation strategy by varing the measure of polymer and carrier. The microspheres of levofloxacin which was formulated were exposed to different physico-chemical parameters like si distribution, solubility studies, FT-IR, drug content, in-vitro dissolution studies, DSC and crys morphology by SEM. FT-IR results has identified no traces of chemical interaction between t polymer and drug. SEM studies determined that the microspheres were framed in spherical a round shape. DSC curve demonstrated that the melting point of the polymer isn't influencing t melting point of the drug and affirmed that no chemical change among drug and polymer. An microbial activity of formulated microspheres shown a substantial zone of inhibition a inhibition of bacterial growth observed. The in-vitro levofloxacin release from optimiz microspheres was initially slow and sustained over the period of time and the cumulative relea was 97% in SF-2 and 91% in CF-3 formulation. The drug release pattern was co-related well w Korsmeyer-Peppas model and was followed by case II non fickian release mechanism.

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INTRODUCTION

A musculo skeletal infection is affecting nearly 2 million patients, most of whom are afflicted with cellulitis or a soft-tissue abscess. Musculo skeletal infections, specifically osteomyelitis, create a substantial burden to the patient treating physician and the health care system as a whole. The definition of osteomyelitis is stated as an inflammatory process of bone and bone marrow caused by an infectious organism which results in local bone obliteration, necrosis and connection of new bone.^[1]

Osteomyelitis can affect both adults and children. The bacteria or fungus that can cause osteomyelitis, however, contrasts among age gathering. The vertebrae and the pelvis part will majorly get affected by osteomyelitis in adults. The adjacent closures of long bones will get affected by osteomyelitis in children. Latest techniques like local delivery of antibiotics have evolved trying to improvise the visualization of Patients with musculoskeletal diseases (osteomyelitis). The usage of local antibiotic delivery systems has been grown as accepted treatment technique that continually evolves for many reasons. There has been a blast new innovation that is intended to encourage the delivery of local antibiotics in new and imaginative ways. The essential purpose for utilizing these local antibiotic delivery vehicles is the capacity to accomplish nearby high local concentrations of antibiotics without associated systemic toxicity. The idea of delivering the drugs locally to the site of disease instead of delivering through the systemic circulation without the concomitant secondary systemic complications is engaging both physiologically and mentally. The ideal local antibiotic delivery system would create high antibiotic levels at the zone of disease and safe drug levels in the systemic circulation. Antibiotics levels would need to be controlled to permit the systemic to be either therapeutic, below the toxic level, or absent, and to allow these features to be controlled independently from each other. Besides, the antibiotic elution curves, the factors that impacts elution, and the most suitable local delivery system for the environment into which the material is to be put, would should to be known. These materials would need to be effectively placed, easily evacuated or changed, patient friendly and inexpensive.^[3]

Recent advance in synthetic chemistry and biotechnology has empowered many drugs candidates to be changed over to therapeutically active agents, along with an enhanced understanding of their cellular functions. In any case, it is not yet possible to control the body distribution of these agents which often causes antagonistic impacts. In addition, high proportion and repeated administrations can result in quick increases in blood concentration of the drugs even to a toxic level. Sustained drug delivery may be one way to improve clinical outcomes, drug delivery to a target site is another promising way to decrease adverse effects.^[2] According to Hanssen, the ideal local antibiotic delivery system “would provide a more efficient delivery of higher levels of antibiotics to the site of infection and yet minimize the risks of systemic toxicity associated with traditional methods of intravenous antibiotics”.^[3]

The standard of local antibiotic delivery has advanced to incorporate the utilization of poly-methyl methacrylate (PMMA) bone cement blended with a combination of heat stable and soluble antibiotics. The antibiotic impregnated PMMA cement can provide structural supports following the expulsion of prostheses and fill an extensive bone imperfection that generally would create an inadequate vascularized environment favourable for bacterial development. Moreover, PMMA with antibiotics can elute high concentrations of medication locally with negligible systemic effects. Although PMMA bone cements were utilized to fortunately anchor prostheses, limitations and problems associated with PMMA had recognized. The potential problems involves the high rate of exothermic property of PMMA that releases only finite number of heat stable antibiotics to be used for treatment, limited antibiotic elution from the superficial area of PMMA that does not achieve complete release of the antibiotics, poor osteointegration with host bone and leachable MMA monomer which may lead to local tissue toxicity and systemic effects such as blood pressure lability, hypoxia and mental confusion.^[1] The development of tissue bioengineering and forging advances has resulted in numerous new releasing materials that have good biocompatibility, are biodegradable, and are capable of osteogenesis, which can be utilized to supplant the PMMA bone cement, such as hydroxyapatite (HA), chitosan, and synthetic polymers. A magnificent amongst the many considered materials is HA. Because HA comprises the major primary segment of bone, it has fine biocompatibility and biological activity and is broadly used for bone tissue repairing and also as a replacement material.^[4, 5] The local installation of biodegradable, slowly eroding antibiotic materials is observed as the best treatment methodology for the disease osteomyelitis.^[6, 7] The carrier furnishes a slower release of antibiotics at the site of infection to eliminate the bacterial infection and reduce the side effects of systemic drugs. Concurrently, the material is gradually degraded and absorbed upon the release of drug; the material induces and encourages new bone formation to recreate the bone distortion, which avoids the second reconstruction of bone defect.^[8]

Henceforth, the objective of this study was to demonstrate calcium hydroxyapatite as an effective carrier for the preparation of levofloxacin filled microspheres to treat osteomyelitis as calcium hydroxyapatite resembles the constituents of bone which has better biocompatibility. The sustained local delivery is best suited for the treatment of osteomyelitis which in turn helps in overcoming the dose dumping.

MATERIALS AND METHOD:

Materials:

Levofloxacin was purchased from yarrow chem products(Mumbai), sodium alginate, chitosan, calcium chloride, sodium tri poly phosphate, potassium dihydrogen phosphate (PDP), sodium hydroxide (NaOH) pellets, orthophosphoric acid, calcium hydroxide (Ca (OH)₂) were of AR grade.

Methods:**Synthesis of Hydroxyapatite (HA) ^[9]**

Aqueous solutions of calcium hydroxide (Ca (OH)₂) and orthophosphoric acid (H₃PO₄, 85%), both of analytical grade, were used as reactants for the preparation of two different types of HA nanoparticles. The first HA powder (HA-1) was synthesized according to the following procedure.

Firstly, 1 L of an aqueous suspension of H₃PO₄ (0.6M) was added drop-by-drop, slowly to a 1 L of an aqueous suspension of Ca (OH)₂ (1M) while stirring vigorously for about 2 h at room temperature. Concentrated NaOH was added until a final pH of 10.5 was obtained. The white solution obtained was washed using de-ionized water and dried in at 80° C for 24 h.

Preparation of hydroxyapatite microspheres:**Preparation of hydroxyapatite microspheres with sodium alginate: ^[10]**

Hydroxyapatite microspheres were prepared with polymers like sodium alginate and calcium chloride by inotropic gelation method. Different trials of levofloxacin were formulated using dissimilar concentration of carrier and polymer. Total 6 formulations were formulated using sodium alginate and hydroxyapatite in dissimilar amount of concentrations. In this method weighed quantity of levofloxacin and hydroxyapatite was added to 100ml sodium alginate solution and thoroughly mixed at 500 rpm. The existing solution was then extruded drop by drop with the help of needle and syringe into 100ml aqueous calcium chloride solution and stirred at 100 rpm. After continual stirring for about 10 minutes the resultant microspheres were washed with water and dried at 60 degrees-2 hours in a hot air oven and stored in desiccator.

Preparation of hydroxyapatite microspheres with chitosan: ^[11]

Chitosan beads were prepared by inotropic cross-linking method. Chitosan was dissolved in glacial acetic acid (2%) to get a clear homogenous mixture. To this add levofloxacin and hydroxyapatite while stirring in magnetic stirrer at the room temperature. The solution was dropped with the help of a syringe into a sodium tri poly phosphate dissolved in water under continuous stirring condition. After continual stirring for 10 minutes the microspheres which obtained were washed in water and then it is dried at 60 degrees for upto 2 hours in a hot air oven and then stored in desiccator.

Table 1: Formulation composition of levofloxacin hydroxyapatite microspheres

Ingredients	SF-1	SF-2	SF-3	SF-4	SF-5	SF-6	CF-1	CF-2	CF-3	CF-4	CF-5	CF-6
Levofloxacin(gms)	0.91	0.91	0.91	0.91	0.91	0.91	0.91	0.91	0.91	0.91	0.91	0.91
Sodium alginate (%)	0.25	0.5	0.75	1	1.25	1.5	-	-	-	-	-	-
Chitosan (%)	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.25	0.5	0.75	1	1.25	1.5
Hydroxyapatite (gms)	1.75	1.5	1.25	1	0.75	0.5	1.75	1.5	1.25	1	0.75	0.5
Calcium chloride (%)	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3
Sodium tri poly phosphate (%)	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3
Distilled water (ml)	Q.S											

Evaluation and characterization of the prepared microspheres**Percentage yield**

The practical percentage yield was calculated from the weight of dried microspheres (practical mass) to the initial weight (theoretical mass) the percentage yield was calculated by using the following formula:

$$\% \text{ Yield} = \frac{\text{Practical Mass}}{\text{Theoretical Mass}} \times 100$$

Particle size analysis

Particle size of formulated microspheres was analyzed with help of optical microscopy. The microscopy was fitted with a stage micrometer and an ocular micrometer. The eyepiece micrometer was calibrated. The diameters of more than 100 microspheres were measured in a random way with help of optical microscope.

Drug excipient compatibility studies:

The compatibility studies of drug and excipient were determined by fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FT-IR) and Differential scanning calorimetry (DSC).

FT-IR spectra for pure drug component and drug-polymer mixture were noted using Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy. The bruker spectrophotometer was used to analyze.

Thermal behaviour of the analyzed samples were investigated using DSC under nitrogen gas at scanning rate of 20°C/min, in the temperature range of 30-300°C.

Scanning electron microscopy (SEM)

The surface and shape characteristics of microspheres were determined by Scanning electron microscopy (SEM).

In vitro drug release studies^[14] and kinetic model of drug release

In-vitro dissolution rate studies for prepared levofloxacin microspheres were conducted in dissolution apparatus II paddle type. The profile of drug release was studied in 900ml of 0.1NHCl at $37\pm 0.5^{\circ}\text{C}$ temperature at 100rpm. The rate of drug release was analyzed at different time intervals of 12, 24, and 48 and till 600 hours by UV visible spectrophotometer (ShimadzuUV1700) at 281nm. Majorly to get to know the mechanism and kinetics of release of drug, the result of the *invitro* dissolution study of microspheres were fitted with various kinetic equations, like zero order¹² (time vs percentage release), first order^[13] (log percentage of drug yet to be released vs time) and Higuchi model (square root of time vs percentage drug release). Correlation co-efficient (r^2) values were calculated for the linear curves that are obtained by regression analysis of the above mentioned plots.

Anti-microbial activity^[15]

A suspension of *S.aureus* was transferred to sterile nutrient agar at 45°C and mixed thoroughly. The mixture was shifted to sterile petridishes to give a depth of 3-4 mm and left to get solidified. Precaution were observed to reduce uniform layer of medium on the plate sterile discs 5 mm in diameters (made from what Mann filter paper) were immersed in the solution of microspheres and maintained an untreated controlled sample for comparison, leave the plate to stand for 1 hrs at room temperature as a period of pre-incubation diffusion to minimize the effects of dissimilarities in different time. Subsequently the plates were incubated at 37°C for 24hrs and contemplated for anti-bacterial activity. The diameter of the zone of inhibition was measured for each plate in which the zone inhibition was observed. The average zone of inhibition was calculated.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

Drug content:

For untreated drug, the drug content was considered to be 100%, it was observed that as the amount of polymer decreases the yield of microspheres increases. A 100% yield cannot be attained substantially due to the adherence of microspheres on to stirring blade. The percentage yields were found to be in the range of 85.66 and 97.50% with 12 different formulations.

Table 2: Observed data for Percentage Yield (%), Drug Content (%), and Avg. Particle size Distribution (μm).

Sl no	Formulations	Percentage Yield (%)	Drug Content (%)	Avg. particle size Distribution (μm)
01	SF-1	93.79	92.18	20
02	SF-2	94.55	94.06	20.4
03	SF-3	98.405	90.93	22
04	SF-4	99.9	93.75	20.5
05	SF-5	85.6	88.12	20.2
06	SF-6	81.25	81.56	20.8
07	CF-1	90.45	80.62	16.1
08	CF-2	83.5	90.93	18.3
09	CF-3	89	87.5	18.5
10	CF-4	95.5	89.06	20.16
11	CF-5	94.95	90.31	18.5
12	CF-6	89.45	80.93	18.4

In-vitro drug release study and kinetics of drug release:

In-vitro dissolution rate studies were conducted by using USP type II dissolution apparatus (rotating basket type). The rate of release at the initial stage (10 days) is slower and it becomes gradual increase in drug release. Levofloxacin molecules that are situated at the surface of the HA is accountable for unrushed initial release of levofloxacin though the release of levofloxacin molecules from the interior of the HA particles by diffusion as well as dissolution processes is responsible for later release. Over the study, 97% of the loaded levofloxacin was successfully released from SF-2 whereas CF-2 formulation releases 91%.

Fig 1: In-vitro drug release data of sodium alginate and levofloxacin microspheres.

Fig 2: In-vitro drug release data of chitosan and levofloxacin microspheres.

Different kinetic model was considered in order to comprehend the in-vitro formulation release profile of the optimized preparation. Optimized formulation best fit with the highest correlation coefficient with korsmeyerspeppas plot. Further the value obtained from the korsmeyers plot i.e., 0.788 (SF-2) and 1.388(CF-3) suggest that the drug release from the microspheres was case II non fickian transport.

Table 3: Release order kinetics of optimized normal microspheres.

Formulation code	Korsmeyer-peppas
SF2	0.788
CF3	1.388

Anti-microbial activity:

S.aureus is the most widely recognized micro-organism found in patients of a wide range of osteomyelitis. Anti-microbial activities of the formulated microspheres against S.aureus are appeared in fig no. 8 SF-2 and CF-3 indicated inhibition zones around the microspheres in which bacterial growth was hindered. Henceforth SF-2 indicated great antimicrobial activity against S.aureus contrasted with CF-3.

Fig 8: Zone of inhibition study.

Table 4: Antimicrobial evaluation of levofloxacin hydroxyapatite microspheres.

Formulation code	Zone of inhibition in mm
SF-2	23
CF-3	18

Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy:

The characteristics absorption peaks of levofloxacin were obtained at 3262.64cm⁻¹, 2935.43cm⁻¹, 3517.54cm⁻¹, 3403.87cm⁻¹. The principle peaks obtained for the combinations were almost similar to that of the drug.

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Fig 3: FT-IR Spectrum of Pure Levofloxacin.

Fig 4: FT-IR Spectrum of Hydroxyapatite.

Fig 5: FT-IR Spectrum of levofloxacin and hydroxyapatite.

Fig 6: FT-IR Spectrum of levofloxacin and sodium alginate.

Fig 7: FT-IR Spectrum of levofloxacin and chitosan.

SEM and DSC Analysis:

The DSC of all the tested physical mixture of drug, and polymer showed the prominent sharp melting peaks as shown in fig no: 9, 10&11 where the melting point of the polymers is not affecting the melting point of the drug therefore it was confirmed that no chemical modification of the drug has taken place and thus they are well matched with each other, hence acceptable for the preparation of microspheres.

In SEM Morphology and appearance of the optimized microspheres (SF-2 and CF-3) were examined by Ultra -55 Carl Zeiss Field Emission Scanning Electron Microscope. As seen from the photograph, the crystals were round and spherical in appearance. Fig no. 12, 13&14.

Fig 9: DSC peak of pure levofloxacin.

Fig 10: DSC peak of levofloxacin and sodium alginate.

Fig 11: DSC peak of levofloxacin and chitosan.

Fig 12: SEM observation of pure levofloxacin.

Fig 13: SEM observation of formulation CF-3 formulation.

Fig 14: SEM observation of formulation SF-2 formulation.

CONCLUSION

Microspheres of levofloxacin were prepared by ionotropic gelation method. In this study the prepared Microspheres of levofloxacin containing Hydroxyapatite as a carrier exhibited good solubility, cumulative drug release from SF-2 formulation was 97% and CF-3 formulation was 91% at initial stage there was a slow release and where in gradually increases day by day. As the measure of polymer enhanced, the concentration of the solution mixture additionally increments. The particle sizes of formulated microspheres were ranged between 30 μ m to 50 μ m. The results of DSC was clearly exhibited no chemical interaction between the polymer and drug. Morphology and appearance of the optimized microspheres were examined by SEM. As seen from the photograph, the microspheres were round and spherical in appearance.

Anti-microbial activity showed inhibition zones around the microspheres in which bacterial growth was inhibited, there was a sustained release of levofloxacin against S.aureus. The drug release profile fits to case II non-fickian transport.

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Conflict of interest:

The authors declare that they have no conflict of interest.

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